

MAXIMUM WORK RATE EXTRACTABLE FROM THE SUN

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ABSTRACT

Solar energy is clean, environmentally friendly, and freely available over the planet. Understanding its real physical limits, imposed by the laws of thermodynamics, allows to establish an adequate baseline for comparison between solar technologies. The operation of solar concentrating systems is based on absorbing incoming solar radiation, converting it into heat, and transferring this heat to a fluid flowing through the collector. The exergy of solar radiation is useful in the preliminary assessment of the performance of solar technologies. A proper model should consider the real physical constraints, to define a useful index. In the present development, further progress has been made by considering the irreversibilities generated in both the high-temperature radiation reservoir and a low-temperature heat sink. This model provides a better understanding of the maximum possible value in CSP systems. The developed model considers a high-temperature radiation reservoir that transfers a heat flux to a work extractor, which rejects heat to a low-temperature sink. The model allows to identify the irreversibilities of an idealized system operating between the sun and the environment.

Keywords: solar radiation, exergy, work extractor, exergy analysis, finite-time thermodynamics

NOMENCLATURE

P	pressure
T	temperature
V	volume
c	speed of light
f	geometric factor
W	Work
Q	Heat
S	Entropy
σ	Stefan-Boltzmann constant
φ	energy flux
ψ	entropy flux
η	efficiency
λ	heat transfer coefficient

1. INTRODUCTION

The consequences of the socio-economic model based on the consumption of fossil fuels have been so dramatic in recent years that no one denies that the current energy model is in crisis and, therefore, in the process of a fast and unstoppable transformation. It is urgent to shift from the current centralized system based on fossil fuels toward a system that is distributed and based on renewable energies.

Among the energies that should make up an important part of the world's energy mix, solar energy undoubtedly stands out. Solar energy is clean, environmentally friendly, and freely available over the planet. Solar energy is used but is not limited to, producing thermal as well as electrical power.

Thanks to the developments that have taken place over the last few decades in those different applications of solar energy, it can be stated that, up to date, some of the technologies have already reached a level of maturity that provides a certain degree of confidence for their deployment.

Currently, many researchers are working in basic and applied science related to the use of solar radiation, however, understanding the real physical limits, imposed by the laws of thermodynamics, allows to establish an adequate baseline for comparison between solar technologies, in this case, solar concentrators for power generation (CSP), and thus, help to make decisions for their implementation.

The operation of solar concentrating systems is based on absorbing incoming solar radiation, converting it into heat, and transferring this heat to a fluid flowing through the collector. These systems are usually analysed in a simple way using the first law of thermodynamics, but this does not consider the degradation of the energy when it is converted or exchanged between streams throughout heat transfer.

To overcome these inconveniences, and establish a firm baseline for a proper comparison, the use of the second law of thermodynamics must be applied to these systems. This is because the exergy efficiency is an index that does not neglect the special properties and boundary conditions of each process.

Over the last 60 years, several researchers such as Petela [1], Spanner [2], Press [3], Parrot [4], Bejan [5], and Badescu [6] had proposed different expressions to define the physical limit of solar radiation. Each one with different approaches that, overestimate the real maximum work rate extractable from solar radiation. The exergy of solar radiation is useful in the preliminary assessment of the performance of solar technologies since the efficiency of the system depends directly on this value, and a proper model should consider the real physical constraints, to define a useful index. In the present work, a further generalization for a work extractor in communication with a high-temperature radiation reservoir and a low-temperature heat sink is considered; thus, a proper physical limit can be stated.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The ability to perform mechanical work has been accepted as a measure of the quality of various kinds of energy, characterizing their ability to be transformed into other kinds of energy. This ability depends on the composition of the considered matter and the environment in which the process takes place [7]. The combination of those parameters determines a figure of merit for a quality index, today known as exergy, that expresses the maximum amount of mechanical work output attainable in the natural environment [7], [8].

Unlike energy, exergy is not conserved, so the exergy balance must be closed by the exergy loss of exergy destruction. For steady-state processes, in which the flow velocities, chemical composition, and thermal parameters are constant at all points of the system, the exergy of the system remains constant [7]–[9].

The exergy transfer rate accompanying heat is usually computed as $\dot{E}x_Q = \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T}\right) \dot{Q}$; however, radiation has to be considered in a different approach from the classical thermodynamic view due to [10]–[12]:

1. The radiative heat transfer between the involved surfaces is at different temperatures
2. The analytical framework of thermodynamics is based on the concept of equilibrium, while for solar processes, this is not the case
3. The use of discrete-particle description of thermal radiation, where two visions are usually adopted:
 - a. Photon gas described by $P = \frac{4\sigma}{3c} T^4$ and $U = \frac{4\sigma}{c} VT^4$
 - b. Radiative flux described by $\varphi = f\sigma T^4$ and $\psi = \frac{4}{3} f\sigma T^3$

Petela [1] considers a cylinder-piston (Fig. 1) with a photon gas inside performing work from a high temperature T_1 up to T_0 , Spanner [2] uses a wider definition of work according to Brønsted to compute the work in a leaf absorbing solar radiation, Press [3] considered a cylinder-piston system with direct and diffuse radiation, Parrot [4] considered the directionality of the photon gas, modifying the previous results, while Bejan [5] considered that the process to extract work must operate

continuously, so he expanded the process of Petela to complete a cycle (Fig. 2). On the other hand, Badescu [6] considers a Müser engine [13] in communication with a high-temperature radiation reservoir and a heat reservoir, as seen in Fig. 3 (alternatively he used a low-temperature radiative reservoir, arguing the possible operation of a system in the space). Under these considerations, the respective efficiencies are:

$$\eta_{\text{Petela}} = 1 - \frac{4T_0}{3T_1} + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{T_0}{T_1}\right)^4 \quad (1)$$

$$\eta_{\text{Spanner}} = 1 - \frac{4T_0}{3T_1} \quad (2)$$

$$\eta_{\text{Press}} = 1 - \frac{4T_0}{3T_1} + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{T_0}{T_1}\right)^4 \quad (3)$$

$$\eta_{\text{Parrot}} = 1 - \frac{4T_0}{3T_1} (1 - \cos \delta)^{1/4} + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{T_0}{T_1}\right)^4 \quad (4)$$

$$\eta_{\text{Bejan}} = 1 - \frac{T_0}{T_1} \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_{\text{Badescu}} = \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_a}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{f_h} \left(\frac{T_a}{T_1}\right)^4\right) \quad (6)$$

FIGURE 1: PETELA SYSTEM [1]

FIGURE 2: BEJAN PROPOSED CYCLE [5]

FIGURE 3: BADESCU HEAT ENGINE [6]

From the models described in the previous section, it is interesting to note the different approaches that have been given to determine the thermal radiation exergy. As highlighted by Castañs [14], de Vos et al. [15], [16], and Bădescu [6], [17]–[19], there are irreversibilities external to the engine that cause the final performance to be lower than Petela's model. Unfortunately, they consider that the conductance between the working extractor and the environment is infinite, so there is no irreversibility in this region (a Müser engine). A particular case was treated by Bădescu [6] when modeling an engine in contact

with two radiation reservoirs at high and low temperatures, which would imply a hypothetical plant operating in space. Thus, it is identified that if the associated irreversibility between the working extractor and the environment is considered, the model would be more appropriate.

To overcome the subtle deficiency of the developed models, consider the system shown in Fig. 4. The photothermal device consists of a work extractor that is in communication with a high-temperature radiation reservoir (at T_H) that will heat the absorber (up to T_a) and run the work extractor with a heat flux (\dot{Q}_a''). According to the second law of thermodynamics (Kelvin-Planck statement [11], [20]), the work extractor (at T_c) must reject heat (\dot{Q}_c'') when in contact with the heat sink (at T_L). Some assumptions must be upheld to define the efficiency of the proposed system shown in Fig. 4:

- The work extractor is not necessarily a reversible device
- The system goes under steady-state operation
- The absorber is considered as a Lambertian black body
- The temperatures are homogeneous at the interfaces
- The energy and entropy fluxes are computed per surface area

FIGURE 4: WORK EXTRACTOR IN COMMUNICATION WITH A HIGH-TEMPERATURE RADIATION RESERVOIR, AND A LOW-TEMPERATURE HEAT SINK

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the aforementioned, it is possible to generate an energy balance in the absorber and the work extractor:

$$\varphi_H - \varphi_a = \dot{Q}_a'' \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{W}'' = \dot{Q}_a'' - \dot{Q}_c'' \quad (8)$$

The energy interaction in the heat reservoir and the heat sink can be described by linear Fourier's law for the diffusion of heat [21], [22]

$$\dot{Q}_c'' = \dot{Q}_L'' = \lambda_c(T_c - T_L) \quad (9)$$

The entropy balance in the work extractor:

$$\frac{\dot{Q}_a''}{T_a} + \dot{S}_{gen}'' = \frac{\dot{Q}_c''}{T_c} \quad (10)$$

The efficiency is defined as the ratio of the work extracted to the radiation absorbed, thus:

$$\eta = \frac{\dot{W}''}{\varphi_H} \quad (11)$$

With Eq. 7-10, it can be shown that the efficiency is:

$$\eta = \left(1 - \frac{1}{f_H} \left[\frac{T_a}{T_H}\right]^4\right) \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_c T_L}{\lambda_c T_a + \sigma(f_H T_H^4 - T_a^4) + T_a \dot{S}_{gen}''}\right) - \frac{\lambda_c T_L T_a \dot{S}_{gen}''}{f_H \sigma T_H^4 [\lambda_c T_a + \sigma(f_H T_H^4 - T_a^4) + T_a \dot{S}_{gen}'']} \quad (12)$$

For a reversible heat engine ($\dot{S}_{gen}'' = 0$):

$$\eta = \left(1 - \frac{1}{f_H} \left[\frac{T_a}{T_H}\right]^4\right) \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_c T_L}{\lambda_c T_a + \sigma(f_H T_H^4 - T_a^4)}\right) \quad (13)$$

An important conclusion can be drawn from Eq. 13 if the conductance of the working extractor is infinite $\lambda_c \rightarrow \infty$, Eq. 6 is retrieved, which is the case of a Müser motor, as done by Bădescu [6], where $T_c \rightarrow T_L$. To obtain the maximum efficiency, the following condition must be met: $\frac{d\eta}{dT_a} = 0$, and can be demonstrated that the resulting equation is an eleventh-degree equation that has no analytical solution:

$$4\sigma^2 T_a^{11} - 8\sigma\lambda_c T_a^8 - 8\sigma^2 f_H T_H^4 T_a^7 + 4\lambda_c^2 T_a^5 - T_a^4 (4T_L \lambda_c^2 - 8\lambda_c \sigma f_H T_H^4 - \lambda_c^2 T_L) - \lambda_c^2 T_L f_H T_H^4 = 0 \quad (14)$$

Solving Eq. 14 for T_a allows defining the optimal temperature that maximizes the efficiency. As stated previously, if the thermal conductance $\lambda_c \rightarrow \infty$, the optimal absorber temperature must be the same as in Bădescu's model [6]; this condition is shown in Fig. 5. The plots in Fig. 6 show the behavior of the optimal absorber temperature, while Fig. 7 the efficiency, for different values of f_H and λ_c , where it can be verified that in the limit case, the values of Bădescu are retrieved.

FIGURE 5: COMPARISON OF THE OPTIMUM TEMPERATURE BETWEEN THE PROPOSED MODEL AND THE DEVELOPED BY BĂDESCU ($f_H = 1$)

FIGURE 6: OPTIMUM ABSORBER TEMPERATURE

FIGURE 7: EFFICIENCY

4. CONCLUSION

The proper model of the maximum work extracted from the sun should not be taken for granted, proof of this is the 60 years of research that have led to different expressions, each one of them eliminating restrictions to obtain more reliable values. In the present development, further progress has been made by considering the irreversibilities generated in both the high-temperature radiation reservoir and a low-temperature heat sink. As a result, this model provides a better understanding of the maximum possible value in CSP systems.

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